

A Quantum Leap towards Reflective Teaching with National Education Policy 2020

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Abstract

The Ministry of Education recently announced the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. The new policy aims to improve literacy and numeracy outcomes in primary schools, decrease dropout rates in middle and secondary schools, and introduce a multidisciplinary approach in the higher education system. Apart from that, the policy focuses on early childhood care by restructuring curriculum and pedagogy, reforming assessments and exams, investing in teacher training, and broadening the scope of teacher evaluation. The present paper aims to study the outlook of school education structure and features of National Education Policy 2020. The focus is to study the concept of Reflective Teaching through a transdisciplinary approach in school education. The nature of the study is descriptive. Analysis and review of the articles for the understanding structure of School education, pedagogical goals of NEP-2020, and reflective level of teaching school level have been done. The core of the paper revolves around Reflective Level Teaching and its implementation through National Education Policy 2020.

Keywords: National Education Policy 2020, Reflective Teaching, Educational Policy, Sustainable Development

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1. Introduction

"Science and Policymaking thrive on challenge and questioning; they are vital to the health of inquiry and Democracy"

Nicholas Stern

Education is a triangular process that includes teachers, learners, and parents. These three form the base of any social structure that humans live within. School teachers play a crucial role in building the foundation years of learners. Teachers lead the community and nation towards development. The subject matter of the education system is one of the core areas of national priorities. Hence, the Government of India introduced National Education Policy in the year 2020 with promising changes in the educational system. National Education Policy aims at harnessing Indian society towards an efficient education system and sustainable development. The country aims towards pre-school and secondary level enrollment of students to be 100 % by 2030, secondary education enrollment should be 50 % by 2030. It is essential to bring changes in educational policy according to the needs of our society. This radical change in the school education system through the recommendations of the National Education Policy will have a major impact on our new generation learners. The New Education Policy-2020 aims to create skill-based human resources capable of reflective thinking. Citizens can promote the economic and social development of the country by contributing their skills. We all naturally reflect on events that occur in our lives from time to time.

2. Review of Related Literature

Fat'hi&Behzadpour(2011)studied that reflective teaching was introduced to the ELT community as a result of the paradigm shift from a positivist to a constructivist perspective, and it grew in popularity following the demise of the method and the "beyond

method" era. Apart from a few potential drawbacks and pitfalls, reflective teaching offers several advantages. Education practitioners and language teachers are provided with a variety of techniques to help them become more self-aware. actions and emotions both inside and outside of the classroom.

Del Carlo et.al (2010) researched that the focus of reflection shifts away from the teacher's actions and toward the teacher's personal growth. This necessitates teachers to connect their identity to their professional careers and examines how teaching helps them achieve their personal life goals. Teachers examine their own identities through this process and are compelled to reflect on the private lives of the students in their classes and how they, as teachers, interact with them have an impact on those lives.

Ali (2017) studied that a reflective approach to teaching entails altering our conventional perceptions of teaching and our role in the process of instruction. As the examples above demonstrate, teachers who critically reflect on their teaching develop changes in attitudes and awareness that they believe can benefit their students and professional development as educators and enhance the level of support they provide their students. As with other forms of self-inquiry, reflective teaching carries some risks, like journaling, It can be time-consuming to write, self-report, or record lessons. However, educators' Reflective analysis of one's teaching is a valuable tool for self-evaluation, according to those who have done so. and professional development. Reflective instruction implies that experience alone is insufficient. professional development, but that experience, when combined with reflection, can be a powerful motivator for educators' development.

3. Significance of the Study

The major function of the policy is to build the overall development

of learners which involves social, emotional, physical, intellectual, moral, and spiritual aspects in the learners. The teacher education system in India promotes the professional development of teachers through various faculty development programs. NCFTE-2009 also mentions about holistic education of learners and is concerned about quality education and pedagogical concerns in the field of teacher education.

4. Objectives

- i. To study the school education structure and recommendations of National Education Policy 2020 for the school education system.
- ii. To study the importance of Reflective Level Teaching in the school curriculum.

5. Methodology

The nature of the study is descriptive. A secondary database is used for data collection and document analysis. Data is collected from different sources like websites, journal articles, e-books reports, NEP 2020 final document, articles published in local papers, national and international, etc.

6. Objective Wise Findings

Objective 1: To study the recommendations of the National Education Policy 2020 for the school education system in India.

National Education Policy 2020 lays particular emphasis on the development of the creative potential of each individual. It is based on the principle that education must develop not only cognitive capacities which include the 'foundational capacities' of literacy and

numeracy and 'higher-order cognitive capacities, such as critical thinking and problem solving - but also social, ethical, and emotional capacities and dispositions - **Ministry of Education (2020)**”

Table 1

The restructured system of school education by National Policy 2020

Foundation Stage	● For 5 Years
Preparatory Stage	● For 3 Years
Middle School Stage	● For 3 Years
Secondary Education Stage	For 4 Years

Key Principles of School Education

- School policy should maintain diversity & local context.
- School environment based on Community participation.
- More focused on learner's conceptual understanding subject-wise.
- It should promote equitable distribution of resources and inclusive education.
- Proper use of Technology and ICT.
- Imparting critical thinking, Problem Solving, reasoning, and creativity.

School Education Structure according to NEP-2020 (Different Stages)	Features
Five-year of Foundation Stage	In the first stage, the foundation stage, children belong to 3 years to 8 years group. In this stage, the child can learn based on activity-based through this activity process development of cognitive, mental, and emotional dimension parameters.
Three-year duration of Preparatory Stage	In this preparatory stage, children belong from 9 years to 11 years. Children can learn with discovery-based and different activity-based methods. Vital for introducing different subjects through inclusive classroom, with the help of textbooks for deeper understanding.
Three-year duration of Middle school education Stage	This Middle school education stage focuses more on constructing knowledge of particular concept form and various disciplines. A semester-based system will be followed. In the Six standards learners can start coding, teachers can facilitate and impart problem-solving skills.
Four-year duration of Secondary education Stage	This stage of secondary school education, follow is a multidisciplinary subject concept with flexible open and exit. Due to a student can any time with his or her choice. Learners can select his or her subject according to choose. Subject pedagogy of courses can learn easily and developed competency. This stage will follow the semester system, in the 10th and 12th standards learners can be followed semester on 5 to 6 subjects.

Table 2

Different stages of school education as per National Education policy 2020

The Salient Features of NEP-2020 on School Education:

- The early childhood education or Foundation stages will focus on the holistic development of the students. Learning should be facilitated with the use of collaborative teaching, logical method, Play-based method, Teamwork, a problem-solving method, and discovery-based learning. More focus is given to subjects like Arts, crafts, games, and music.
- According to NEP-2020, school education should focus on competency-based learning, digitalization, inclusion, integration on school subjects, use of ICT devices, and creation of scientific temperament.
- STEAM method should be applied for preparing textbooks, syllabus according to learners' needs. STEAM means (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts & Design, and Mathematics) model.
- The examination system should be flexible and student-friendly. It should not be only focused on evaluative purposes but also on the overall assessment of the learners. Concept understanding, highorder thinking skills, practical experience are the core areas that the learning and teaching process should focus on.
- Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) should be included in the assessment process of the students. There should be a System of Continuous tracking of the learners. National Testing

Agency (NTA) should conduct common aptitude tests for all learners.

- Assessment should include different methods like project-based assignment quizzes, role plays, assignments, group work, portfolios, etc. to assess the psychomotor, cognitive, affective progress for learners.
- More importance should be given to regional language and a mother tongue for teaching classes 5 to 8.
- Establishment of “Bal Bhavan” and “Samajik Chetna Kendras” for the development of the social and intellectual dimension of a child.
- School Quality Assessment and Accreditation Framework (SQAAF) to be created for the accreditation and maintenance of quality and standard in the schools.
- Reduce gap for socially and economically weaker section children, disabled children's sections, and children with special needs in the manner of Inclusive classroom.
- Quality maintenance for the school education section by SQAAF, SSSA, and self-disclosure on the school website.

NEP 2020 and Educational Goals

- Build the concept of understanding of abstract.
- Articulation of different subjects.
- Experiential learning with the project-based method for every subject.

- Way of learning, how to learn, why to learn, what you learn etc.
- Day to day culture activity, social activity learning.
- Development of critical thinking, problem-solving, reasoning, etc.
- Focus on key concepts will be upon the content.
- Discussion and group-based learning.
- Collaboration method for deeper understanding of teaching-learning.

Objective2: To study the importance of Reflective Level Teaching in the school curriculum.

Reflective Level of Teaching at School

The reflective level of teaching is called the highest level of teaching. Morris L. Biggedefines reflection as, a "careful, critical examination of the idea or supposed article of knowledge in the light of testing evidence which supports it and the further conclusions towards which it points". It deals with ULT (Upper level of teaching) according to the mental ability of the learners.

Fig. 1: Gibb's Reflective Cycle

Source: The University of Kent depicting Gibb's Reflective Cycle.

Key Behavior of Reflective Teachers

- Regard child's perception as most important
- Have direct contact with children
- Create an Effective learning classroom
- Nurture the children with love
- Reflect on subjective knowledge
- Use child-centric assessment strategies

Scope of Reflective Level Teaching in School Education

- It develops creative, original, and independent thinking among students. It is a free-floating situation.
- It grows more with a unique relationship where the minds of teaching and students are engaged in any different nature of formal course material.
- It makes learning enjoyable and a hands-on experience.

Suggestions on Reflective Level of Teaching at School Education

Reflective teaching can be used in different dimensions of school education:

- Reflective Teaching should be followed systematically, only then it will have a positive effect in achieving the goals of the National Education Policy, 2020.
- The teacher should create a problematic situation that may develop the original and creative thinking of the learner.
- The students should feel about the problem so they may formulate the schema to explore the possible solutions of the students.
- The learner should be objective in collecting the evidence for the problem and drawing the conclusion.

An initiative by Government of India to Promote Reflective Teaching-Learning through NEP 2020:

Ek Bharat Shrestha Bharat

Every student in the country will participate in a fun project or activity on 'The Languages of India' during Grades 6-8 as part of the 'Ek Bharat Shrestha Bharat' initiative. They will learn about the languages' origins, scripts, and so on. Additionally, students will learn which geographical areas speak which languages and will learn to say "commonly spoken phrases and sentences in each major Indian language, as well as a bit about each language's rich and uplifting literature. -**Ministry of Education**"

7. Conclusion

Reflective teaching can formalize the process. Students are frequently required to write their reflections as a blog or reflective report. This inculcates a habit in students that are deemed beneficial for developing into more reflective learner. Encouraging reflective practice in schools benefits not only individual teachers but also the entire school. By establishing a culture of reflective practice, schools can improve by establishing a solid foundation for continuous improvement in teaching and learning. It communicates the importance of learning to both students and teachers, and that everyone is committed to promoting it. It fosters collaboration by encouraging teachers to reflect on and adapt their own and their colleagues' practices. Teachers can collaborate, pool their resources, and offer support to one another. This contributes to the development of best practices throughout the school, which results in a more productive working environment.

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